

To Assess the Range Comorbidities in Severe Acute Malnutrition Accompanied by Unexpected Electrolyte Imbalances during Episodes of Diarrhoea.

Baibhav Prakash Sahay¹, Abu Irfan², S. Bhushan³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

³Professor and HOD, Department of Pediatrics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

Received: 14-01-2024 / Revised: 06-02-2024 / Accepted: 25-02-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Abu Irfan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the study was to evaluate the spectrum of co-morbidities in severe acute malnutrition with unexpected dyselectrolytemia in diarrhea.

Methods: The observational study was carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. Total 200 Children upto 5 years aged, admitted in Nutritional Rehabilitation Centre of Department of Paediatrics, were include in this study. Various co morbid conditions in study population were identified. All the laboratory examination was done with standard method.

Results: Majority of children with SAM were having co-morbidity in the form of Anaemia (90%), Diarrhoea (64%) followed by pneumonia (30%), Rickets (27%), Tuberculosis (16%), Otitis media (16%), UTI (10%), Celiac (8%), Hypothyroidism (5%), & HIV (3%). 140 (70%) SAM children presented with diarrhea out of which Hyponatremia was in 100 cases & Hypernatremia was in 5 cases. No statistically significant difference was found with hyponatremia in diarrheal or non-diarrheal cases of SAM (P value of 0.07). Potassium levels of children with diarrheal & non diarrheal children with SAM. Serum Potassium levels of 200 SAM children were analysed. It was found that 45 SAM children were having hypokalemia. Hypokalemia was found in 30 diarrheal cases & 15 in non- diarrheal cases. A statistically significant difference was found with hypokalemia in SAM (P value of 0.025) between Diarrheal & Non diarrheal cases.

Conclusion: We concluded that dyselectrolytemia is high in complicated SAM and mainly sodium disturbances in form of hyponatremia are common in different co-morbid conditions. Hence, we recommend that due care is to be given for management of dyselectrolytemia in complicated SAM children.

Keywords: Co-morbidities, Dyselectrolytemia, Potassium, Severe acute malnutrition, Sodium

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Introduction

Malnutrition, a common problem worldwide and globally 20 million children suffer from Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM), with the major burden being in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. [1] In South East Asia mortality rate ranges from 5-40%, and complicated SAM has a case fatality rate of over 30% in some series even when WHO recommended management is followed. [2-4]

Children with SAM are categorized into “complicated and uncomplicated cases” based on clinical criteria. SAM children with complications require inpatient management and those without complications can be treated on a community basis.

World Health Organization (WHO) states this as a strong recommendation with low-quality evidence. [5] As per the WHO, serum electrolytes are measured and supplemented (potassium and magnesium) only in SAM children with complications. SAM children without complications are managed in community with Ready to Use Therapeutic Food (RUTF) which is enriched with minerals and micronutrients. [6] In our country, as RUTF is not available, children are advised home-based energy dense food along with micronutrient supplements. Hence, their diet may still be deficient in minerals. Diarrhea and pneumonia accounts for

approximately half the under-five deaths in India and malnutrition is believed to contribute to 61% of diarrheal deaths and 53% pneumonia deaths. Malnutrition increases the risk and worsens the severity of infections. [7] SAM children are more prone to severe infections that culminates into different co-morbid conditions and consequentially leads to electrolyte derangement due to reductive adaptation Na⁺, K⁺, ATPase systems of the body begin to ‘shut down’. Regulation of Na⁺/K⁺ depends upon excretion, intake, absorption occurs through gastrointestinal system. Disorders of Na⁺/K⁺ homeostasis can occur due to excessive loss, gain or retention of the Na⁺/K⁺ or H₂O. A vigorous imbalance of these two ions causes hyponatremia/ hypokalemia and hypernatremia/hypokalemia. Remarkably, hypokalemia and hyponatremia are seen more frequently in diarrheal population than non-diarrheal. [8]

Malnourished hospitalized children have a higher rate of complications, increased mortality, longer length of hospital stay and increased hospital costs. Lack of infrastructure for growth monitoring and regular institutional assessments are responsible for the persistence and delayed detection of malnutrition in these children. A better nutritional status is associated with better survival and better outcomes. After clinical improvement, aggressive nutritional management is the mainstay in the care of these children and is a more promising strategy to improve outcome.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the spectrum of co-morbidities in severe acute malnutrition with unexpected dyselectrolytemia in diarrhea.

Materials and Methods

The observational study was carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. Total 200 Children upto 5 years aged, admitted in Nutritional Rehabilitation Centre of Department of Paediatrics, were include in this study. Various co morbid conditions in study population were identified. All the laboratory examination was done with standard method.

Study Procedure: Complete history and systemic examination were. Various co morbid conditions in study population were identified and managed accordingly. Laboratory examination was done.

- Hemoglobin by Lab Life 3D hematological autoanalyzer & anaemia was defined as per WHO guidelines.
- Total leucocyte count by Lab Life 3D hematological autoanalyzer.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was done, using the statistical package for social science (SPSS 25.0) for Windows Software. Continuous variables were expressed as means, standard deviation (SD), confidence intervals (95%CI), frequency and range. Chi-square was applied and P value of < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1: Co morbid conditions in SAM

Co-morbidity	No. of cases	% Percentage
Diarrhoea	128	64
Tuberculosis	32	16
Pneumonia	60	30
Otitis media	32	16
UTI	22	11
Rickets	54	27
Anaemia	180	90
Celiac disease	16	8
Hypothyroidism	10	5
HIV	6	3

Majority of children with SAM were having co-morbidity in the form of Anaemia (90%), Diarrhoea (64%) followed by pneumonia (30%), Rickets (27%), Tuberculosis (16%), Otitis media (16%), UTI (10%), Celiac (8%), Hypothyroidism (5%), & HIV (3%).

Table 2: Dysnatremia in SAM children in diarrheal & non diarrheal groups

Serum Sodium	No diarrhea	Diarrhea	Total (%)
Hyponatremia	40	100	140 (70%)
Normonatremia	20	35	55 (27.50%)
Hypernatremia	0	5	5 (2.5%)
Total cases	60	140	200

140 (70%) SAM children presented with diarrhea out of which Hyponatremia was in 100 cases & Hypernatremia was in 5 cases. No statistically significant difference was found with hyponatremia in diarrheal or non-diarrheal cases of SAM (P value of 0.07).

Table 3: Hypokalemia in SAM children

Serum Potassium	No diarrhea	Diarrhea	Total
Normokalemia	45	110	155
Hypokalemia	15	30	45
Total	60	140	100

Potassium levels of children with diarrheal & non diarrheal children with SAM. Serum Potassium levels of 200 SAM children were analysed. It was found that 45 SAM children were having hypokalemia. Hypokalemia was found in 30 diarrheal cases & 15 in non- diarrheal cases. A statistically significant difference was found with hypokalemia in SAM (P value of 0.025) between Diarrheal & Non diarrheal cases.

Discussion

Malnutrition is a major global problem [9] which interacts with diarrhea in a vicious cycle leading to high morbidity and mortality in children and it is as well as a complicating factor for other illness in developing countries. Malnourished children have long lasting, severe and recurrent diarrhea. The prevalence of diarrhea is 5-7 times more in malnourished as compared to normal children. [10] In malnutrition various abnormalities occur in body electrolytes which become more pronounced with diarrheal incidence since electrolytes conduct an electrical current, helps to balance pH and facilitate the passage of fluid between and within cells through process of osmosis imparting in regulation of the function of neuromuscular, endocrine and excretory systems. [11,12] Children with SAM are categorized into "complicated and uncomplicated cases" based on clinical criteria. SAM children with complications require inpatient management and those without complications can be treated on a community basis. World Health Organization (WHO) states this as a strong recommendation with low-quality evidence. [5]

Majority of children with SAM were having co-morbidity in the form of Anaemia (90%), Diarrhoea (64%) followed by pneumonia (30%), Rickets (27%), Tuberculosis (16%), Otitis media (16%), UTI (10%), Celiac (8%), Hypothyroidism (5%), & HIV (3%). In present study anaemia was found in 88% which was higher than 51% from Columbia as reported by Bernal C et al 2008. [13] 65% of children with SAM in present study was admitted with diarrhea as a co-morbid state which is in accordance with 60% from Bangladesh as reported by Khanum et. Al [14] but lower than 67% from Zambia as reported by Irena et. Al [15] 68% from Columbia as reported by Bernal C. et al [13] 70% from Kenya as reported by Nzioki et al [16] which

may be due to geographical factor while higher than 54% from Madhya Pradesh as reported by Kumar et al [17] 49% from Kenya as reported by Talbert et al [18] and 11% from Bangladesh as reported by Hossain et al [19] It may be because of low socioeconomic status, bottle feeding & unhygienic feeding can be contributed to this high prevalence of diarrhea in present study. 15% of Children with SAM were diagnosed as a Pulmonary tuberculosis in a present study which is higher than 2%, 5.6%, 6.6%, 9% and 9.3% from Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Ethiopia, Bangladesh and Uttar Pradesh as reported by Bhat et al [20] and Gangaraj. [21]

27% SAM children in our study had ricketic features, and this was comparable with the previous reports. [22] This can be contributed to dietary deficiency and Vitamin D supplementation in early period of life. 3% of children with SAM were diagnosed with hypothyroidism in the present study based on clinical features suggestive of hypothyroidism. Exact prevalence of hypothyroidism was not found because selected cases were investigated. 3% of children with SAM were diagnosed HIV positive in the present study which is lower than found in previous studies. [23] This may be because of low prevalence of HIV in present study. However high prevalence of HIV infection in children with SAM in African country may be associated with nutritional deficiencies secondary to decreased nutrient intake, impaired nutrient absorption, increased nutrient losses and increased nutrient demand. This is due to direct effect of HIV and the myriad of opportunistic infections precipitated by HIV induced immunodeficiency.

140 (70%) SAM children presented with diarrhea out of which Hyponatremia was in 100 cases & Hypernatremia was in 5 cases. No statistically significant difference was found with hyponatremia in diarrheal or non-diarrheal cases of SAM (P value of 0.07). Potassium levels of children with diarrheal & non diarrheal children with SAM. Serum Potassium levels of 200 SAM children were analysed. It was found that 45 SAM children were having hypokalemia. Hypokalemia was found in 30 diarrheal cases & 15 in non- diarrheal cases. A statistically significant difference was found with hypokalemia in SAM (P value of 0.025) between Diarrheal & Non diarrheal cases.

Conclusion

We concluded that dyselectrolytemia is high in complicated SAM and mainly sodium disturbances in form of hyponatremia are common in different comorbid conditions. Hence, we recommend that due care is to be given for management of dyselectrolytemia in complicated SAM children.

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